

Key	Title	DOI	Source	Excluded?	Relevant for?	Skimmed?
Zuiderwijk2014	Innovation with open data: Essential elements of open data ecosystems	10.3237	Initial Scoping Search		Open Data	1
Terrizzano2015	Data Wrangling: The Challenging Journey from the Wild to the Lake		Initial Scoping Search		Open Data	1
Bhardwaj2015	Collaborative Data Analytics with DataHub	10.1477	Initial Scoping Search		Open Data	1
Smith2021	Enabling Collaborative Data Science Development with the Ballet Framework	10.1145	Initial Scoping Search		Open Data	1
Dawes2016	Planning and designing open government data programs: An ecosystem approach	10.1016	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Ruijter2017a	Open data for democracy: Developing a theoretical framework for open data use	10.1016	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Ruijter2017b	Connecting societal issues, users and data. Scenario-based design of open data platforms	10.1016	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Abella2019	The process of open data publication and reuse	10.1002	Google Scholar		Open Data	1
Tejeda2020	A user-centered process for the analysis and visualization of open data sets		Google Scholar		Open Data	1
Bumann2021	Predicting the spread of invasive marine species with open data and machine learning: Process and Challenges		Google Scholar		Open Data	1
Ruijter2019	Open Government Data as an Innovation Process: Lessons from a Living Lab Experiment	10.1080	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Alexopoulos2014	A platform for closing the open data feedback loop based on web2.0 functionality	10.2937	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Choi2017	Characteristics of collaboration in the emerging practice of open data analysis	10.1145	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Kassen2018	Adopting and managing open data: Stakeholder perspectives, challenges and policy recommendations	10.1108	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Kjaergaard2020	Current practices and infrastructure for open data based research on occupant-centric design and operation of buildings	10.1016	Scopus Search		Open Data	1
Crusoe2019	Users' activities for using open government data—a process framework	10.1108	Google Scholar		Open Data	1
Magalhaes2015	Open government data intermediaries: a terminology framework		Snowballing 1		Open Data	1
Lnenicka2019	Big and open linked data analytics ecosystem: Theoretical background and essential elements	10.1016	Snowballing 1		Open Data	1
Davies2010	Open data, democracy and public sector reform. A Look at Open Government Data Use from Data. Gov. UK		Snowballing 1	Not peer-reviewed	Open Data	1
Pollock2011	https://blog.okfn.org/2011/03/31/building-the-open-data-ecosystem/		Snowballing 1	Not peer-reviewed	Open Data	1
Schweiger2014	Open data: Challenges and opportunities for transit agencies		Scopus Search	Not peer-reviewed		1
Wang2019	Human-AI Collaboration in Data Science: Exploring Data Scientists' Perceptions of Automated AI	10.1145	Initial Scoping Search	Not open data		1
Zhang2020	How do Data Science Workers Collaborate? Roles, Workflows, and Tools	10.1145	Initial Scoping Search	Not open data		1
Kucera2011	Methodologies and Best Practices for Open Data Publication		Initial Scoping Search	Not focused on u		1
Kim2019	Overview of disciplinary data sharing practices and promotion of open data in science	10.6087	Google Scholar	Not focused on u		1
Zhang2021	A review of open research data policies and practices in China	10.5334	Google Scholar	Not focused on u		1
Conrado2017	Open innovation: Towards sharing of data, models and workflows	10.1016	Google Scholar	Not focused on u		1
Hartung2010	Open data kit: tools to build information services for developing regions	10.1145	Initial Scoping Search	Not data enginee		1
Roh2021	A Survey on Data Collection for Machine Learning: A Big Data - AI Integration Perspective	10.1109	Initial Scoping Search	Not data enginee		1
Baack2015	Datafication and empowerment: How the open data movement re-articulates notions of democracy, participation, and journalism	10.1177	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
DeVocht2015	A visual exploration workflow as enabler for the exploitation of linked open data		Google Scholar	Not data enginee		1
Morelli2018	Open data: creating communities and practices for a new common	10.1007	Google Scholar	Not data enginee		1
Morelli2017	Framing design to support social innovation: the Open4Citizens project	10.1080	Snowballing 1	Not data enginee		1
Ruijter2018	Open data work: understanding open data usage from a practice lens	10.1177	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Riginos2020	Building a global genomics observatory: Using GEOME (the Genomic Observatories Metadatabase) to expedite and improve depositio	10.1111	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Mutuku2012	Increasing kenyan open data consumption: A design thinking approach	10.1145	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Quix2017	Business process modelling for a data exchange platform		Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Park2022	Open data innovation: Visualizations and process redesign as a way to bridge the transparency-accountability gap	10.1016	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Begany2017	An open health data engagement ecosystem model: Are facilitators the key to open data success?	10.1002	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Slobodova2020	Zooming Into the Ecosystem: Agency and Politics Around Open Data Platforms in Lyon and Berlin	10.3389	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Kawashita2022	Open Government Data Use in the Brazilian States and Federal District Public Administrations	10.3390	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Shehata2021	Saudi scholars' perceptions and use of open government data portals at Shaqra University, Saudi Arabia	10.1177	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Corbett2020	Integrating across sustainability, political, and administrative spheres: A longitudinal study of actors' engagement in open data ecosyste	10.1770	Scopus Search	Not data enginee		1
Mauthner2013	Open access digital data sharing: Principles, policies and practices	10.1080	Google Scholar	Not data enginee		1
Gonzalez-Zapata20	The multiple meanings of open government data: Understanding different stakeholders and their perspectives	10.1016	Snowballing 1	Not data enginee		1
Freitas2020	A critical study of electronic participation, transparency and open data in two Latin American countries	10.1504	Scopus Search	Not accessible		1
Kronkosky2017	Improved oil recovery estimation with data analytic methods: A workflow for open data analysis	10.2116	Scopus Search	Not accessible		
Angeles2019	Advancing resilient and sustainable buildings through a new normative workflow for integrated life-cycle assessments	10.1067	Scopus Search	Not accessible		
Shi2022	Estimating housing vacancy rates at block level: The example of Guiyang, China	10.1016	Scopus Search	Not accessible		
Bhardwaj2014	DataHub: Collaborative Data Science & Dataset Version Management at Scale		Initial Scoping Search	No workflow desc		1
Beno2017	Perception of key barriers in using and publishing open data	10.2937	Scopus Search	No workflow desc		1
MercadoLara2014	Open government and data intermediaries: The case of aiddata	10.1145	Scopus Search	No workflow desc		1
Wang2018	An analysis of interaction between users and open government data portals in data acquisition process	10.1007	Google Scholar	No workflow desc		1
Torino2020	Semantic enrichment for open data availability: Theory and practice [Enriquecimento Semântico Para A Disponibilização De Dados Ab	10.5007	Scopus Search	Language not sp		1
Lnenicka2020	Big and open linked data analytics: a study on changing roles and skills in the higher educational process	10.1180	Google Scholar	Duplicate		1